

Sustainability Through ICTs: Special Focus on E-Waste Management and Circular Economy

Aprajita Sharrma

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List of Abbreviations

4R:	Refuse, Reduce, Reuse and Recycle
CAGR:	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CRC:	Centres for Refurbishing of Computers
E-waste:	Electronic waste
EEE:	Electrical and Electronic Equipment
EPR:	Extended Producer Responsibility
FPO:	Farmer Producer Organisations
ICT:	Information Communication Technology
ILO:	International Labour Organization
IT:	Information Technology
ITU:	International Telecommunication Union
MoEFCC:	Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change
Mt:	Metric Tons
NCDC:	National Cooperative Development Corporation
NGO:	Non-Governmental Organisation
PCB:	Polychlorinated Biphenyls
PROs:	Producer Responsibility Organisations
SEBRAE:	Brazilian Support Service for Micro and Small Enterprises
TRAI:	Telecom Regulatory Authority of India
UNITAR:	United Nations Institute for Training and Research
WEEE:	Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment

Abstract

The electronic and information communication technology (ICT) industries are overwhelming consumers by releasing a variety of electronic products in the market. India is the third largest generator of electronic waste (e-waste). The increasing consumption of electronic products leads to improper disposal, giving rise to serious environmental and public health repercussions. To make the matter worse, the e-waste management in India is largely unorganised, as is the case with other emerging economies, resulting in ignorance about limiting the toxicity of e-waste. Due to a lack of information on the unorganised sector, the collection process of e-waste and the state of its recycling status often go unreported. To address this issue, a cooperative model may prove to be effective. However, there is limited academic literature on the scope of the cooperative model in formalising the Indian e-waste management ecosystem. Incidentally, the infrastructure for collection and disposal is inadequate, along with budgetary limitations. Inefficient recycling facilities and lack of technological advancements could also be a great setback in implementing such a model. To address this, a large-scale sensitisation programme, devised in collaboration with legal workers' associations, is critical for bringing all the stakeholders together. Through a qualitative analysis of case studies delving into formalisation efforts made by organisations such as Chintan (Environmental Research and Action Group), a New Delhi-based NGO (Non-Governmental Organisation) that works towards sustainable waste management, environmental justice, and the empowerment of waste pickers through inclusive and innovative solutions, and the Government of Brazil to extend the responsibility to manufacturers and industries, this paper addresses the gaps in current e-waste management in India. The paper argues that initiating a network of private organisations, informal workers and civil society organisations benefits all stakeholders involved in the e-waste management ecosystem. Furthermore, such a facilitation will also ensure the disposal and recycling of e-waste in an environmentally friendly manner. The case studies provide a model for the government to initiate a formal circular e-waste management economy.

Keywords: E-Waste Management, Informal Sector, Cooperative Model, Formalisation, Circular Economy.

1. Introduction

There is an increasing challenge due to indiscriminate production and disposal of electronic products, due to increased disposable incomes, changing designs, and frequent want to upgrade electronic products. Electronic and ICT industries are inundating markets with new designs, upgrades in existing models and rapid speed of production, which has worsened environmental concerns due to ever-increasing e-waste. Toxic waste has adverse consequences on health especially that of children, pregnant women, and workers in the unorganised sector involved in waste disposal and metal extraction from e-waste, soil and agricultural produce.

The United Nations Institute for Training and Research (UNITAR) and the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) together released the Global E-Waste Monitor 2024, which presents a worrisome image of the rapidly growing worldwide e-waste issue. A frightening 62 million tonnes of electrical waste was produced globally in 2022 alone, a record amount that represents an 82% rise over 2010. According to projections, if current trends continue, the amount of e-waste generated annually worldwide might reach 82 million tonnes by 2030. Arguably, the most urgent issue raised in the study is the disconnect between the production of e-waste and recycling initiatives. Merely 22.3% of the material was properly recovered and repurposed in 2022, despite the massive volume created. This indicates that almost three-quarters of potentially hazardous and valuable goods wind up in landfills or unofficial recycling yards. The analysis estimates that \$91 billion worth of recoverable elements, such as copper, gold, and iron, were found in the 2022 global e-waste monitor report, indicating the startling amount of value wasted. However, the vast majority of these resources are squandered since recycling systems are either ineffective or inadequate in many areas, which leads to both missed economic opportunity and environmental deterioration (Baldé et al., 2024).

ICTs' environmental impact is both direct and indirect - running ICT systems like data centres, servers, telecom towers, etc., requires more energy. Discarded electrical and electronic equipment (EEE), including phones, laptops, refrigerators, sensors, and televisions, is commonly referred to as e-waste or waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE). This category encompasses a wide range of household and personal devices, such as computers, smart gadgets, screens, tablets, and heating or cooling appliances. Both direct and indirect exposure to e-waste, either through physical contact or inhalation of

toxic fumes, poses serious health risks to humans and animals. When e-waste accumulates in soil, water, air, and other natural resources, it enters the food chain. This can lead to the formation of toxic by-products that metabolise very slowly in the human body, potentially resulting in long-term health effects such as cancer, respiratory and hormonal disorders, immunodeficiency diseases, birth defects, and even infant mortality. Children and young adults are particularly susceptible to these risks due to their developing bodies. Compounding the issue is the rapid global rise in e-waste, driven by increased consumption of EEE, shorter product life cycles, and the limited availability and high cost of repair options. As a result, e-waste has become the fastest-growing stream of domestic waste worldwide (World Health Organization, 2024).

In 2022, the Asia region generated the highest amount of e-waste (30,147 million kg), followed by the Americas region (14,427 million kg), the Europe region (13,076 million kg) and the Africa region (3551 million kg) (Baldé et al., 2024).

The World Health Organization asserts that threats posed by e-waste to the environment and human health could be significantly reduced through proper disposal. Initiatives such as the Packaging Recovery Organisation Europe, collection from various stakeholders, secure transportation facilities along with storage and safety measures may address some of the challenges of e-waste.

In India, the government focuses on developing green ICT solutions. The regulator- the Telecom Regulatory Authority of India (TRAI), National Telecom Policy 2012 (Ministry of Communications and Information Technology, 2012), the draft of National Digital Communications Policy 2018 (Government of India, 2018), and the visions of Prime Minister Narendra Modi on sustainability further underline the significance of green technology. TRAI's Recommendations for Green Energy Solutions (TRAI, 2011) and the Consultation Paper on Approach towards Sustainable Telecommunications (TRAI, 2017) also confirm the aspiration and state that the ICT industry must endeavour to attain sustainable development goals and immediate action is required to mitigate climate change through technology development. It is argued that ICTs can positively contribute to the reduction of carbon footprint by not only enhancing the use of renewable energy sources to run production units but also by using environment-friendly products in the production of electronic goods (Radu, 2014).

Despite its aspirations to address the challenges, India remains the world's third-largest source of e-waste, generating around 3.2 million tonnes in 2019, behind only China (10 million tonnes) and the US (6.9 million tonnes) (Forti et al., 2020).

Mumbai tops the list of top ten cities generating the highest amount of e-waste, followed by Delhi, Bengaluru, Chennai, Kolkata, Ahmadabad, Hyderabad, Pune, Surat and Nagpur, respectively (Chatterjee, n.d.). 70% of e-waste is generated by the government, public and private sectors, followed by individual households, which contribute 15% and the remaining 15% is produced by manufacturers (“Bangalore third in e-waste”, 2013). According to a recent survey by the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, approximately 85.5% of Indian households possess at least one smartphone (Suneja, 2025). Given the increasing dependence of human life on technology, the volume of e-waste will increase multi-fold, which will require increased focus on early measures towards e-waste management.

E-waste contains hazardous substances like arsenic, liquid crystal, lithium, mercury, nickel, polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), selenium, barium, brominated flame-proofing agent, cadmium, chrome, cobalt, copper, and lead, which are toxic and carcinogenic in nature. If e-waste is handled unprofessionally and processed in a crude manner, it can wreak havoc on the human body and environment (Sundararaju, 2018).

Towards the goal of safer e-waste management, India amended its e-waste policy in 2018, prepared by the Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change (MoEFCC). Some of the salient features of the rules include e-waste classification, extended producer responsibility (EPR), recognition of producer responsibility organisations (PROs) and restrictions on the import of e-waste containing hazardous materials (MoEFCC, 2023b).

In this context, the discourse on e-waste management must shift its focus to the informal sector and its role in e-waste management policy. Informal collectors and recyclers of waste (also referred to as waste pickers) carry out these activities owing to a high demand for secondary raw materials (recyclables) and a shortage in the provision of these public services. Their work is characterised by low entry barriers, absence of organisation levels, negligible bargaining power and low incomes for most workers at the bottom of the value chain. Therefore, there is a need to outline the significance of integrating the informal sector into the formal sector for effective e-waste management. To enable this, a cooperative model is suggested to ensure the synergy between the formal sector’s processing capability and the collection efficiency of the informal sector. Cooperatives have the ability to address the capacity and capital constraints of the unorganised sector, enabling them to provide economies of scale. A cooperative model is highly recommended to increase the efficiency of the

informal e-waste sector by fully utilising the capabilities and processing methodologies of the formal sector. This would also increase the collection strategies of the informal sector by making it more efficient, with the utilisation of new-age technology.

The cooperative approach will further manage the revenue constraints, helping with cost advantages and improving capacity with efficient production of the unorganised sector.

This approach also removes the middlemen, enhancing and improving price discovery for the unorganised workers, it also provides them with the advantage of collective bargaining capacity and the ability to compete with larger companies. This approach will also help them in getting into the mainstream commercial operations, as we have seen in the cases of milk cooperatives like Amul in India and also in the case of sugar sector.

If e-waste is managed in a scientific and sustainable manner in India, the potential for revenue generation and recovery is extensive. The fully egalitarian process of resolving issues and disputes, joint proprietorship, finding various options, ways, and means towards new business modules will enhance economic freedom and capital generation. Cooperatives have a common profit-driven model, are pliable, and have shared values and objectives.

In India, we have already witnessed the White Revolution in the form of dairy cooperatives, which has hugely benefited farmers, empowered them, warranted them greater financial freedom, making them well equipped by offering them collective bargaining power and market presence. Another such example is Land O'Lakes cooperative in the UK, where the Amul-like model has been extremely successful and profitable.

The role played by the governments in these cases is extremely important as all the gaps and lacunas in the sector can be assessed and addressed, and a more conducive solution may be prepared for the informal sector to better equip it in competing with the formal sector.

2. Literature Review

Various studies have been conducted where it has been proven time and again that wherever waste management cooperatives have been established, there has been a phenomenal increase in revenue generation due to formalisation and recognition of the informal sector. Not only has it leveraged the collective bargaining power of the cooperatives, but it has also tremendously improved the day-to-day work environment. It has also protected the workers socio-economically (Gunsilius et al., 2011). Various case studies in Latin America and Asia have time and again shown that this approach has helped bridge the gap between the commercial demand and availability of recycled materials while ensuring better working and financial conditions for the workers (Medina, 2000). Case reports from India and Brazil (International Labour Organization [ILO], 2014) have shown that wherever national policies support such cooperatives and are mandated by collective responsibility between all the actors, it has always proven mutually beneficial. For example, India's e-waste management regulations and Brazil's National Solid Waste Management Policy 2010 focus on reducing the gap between the formal and informal sectors and amalgamate the informal sector with NGOs such as Chintan (Chaturvedi & Bhardwaj, 2013).

This integration benefits both sectors, promoting price discovery, welfare goals, and green jobs (Dutta & Goel, 2021). However, policy implementation remains inconsistent, as seen in Colombia (Saget et al., 2022).

3. Methodology and Data

Secondary sources such as qualitative studies, government documents and reports have been referred to arrive at suggestions for effective e-waste management involving the informal sector. Case studies of emerging economies have been used to justify the policy recommendations and address the opportunities and gaps existing in the present scenario in India. Most of the case studies and reports provide an in-depth analysis based on focus group discussions and open-ended interviews conducted in the past. Inferences from previous studies and research papers have been made to justify certain policy prescriptions for the effective integration of the informal sector in e-waste management policy. Various state interventions and NGO initiatives are cited to supplement the suggestions and recommendations given in the paper.

4. Case Studies: Informal Sector Integration in E-Waste Management

The following case studies provide insight into how integration of the informal sector can be facilitated. The case studies demonstrate the benefits of mutual gains in bridging the formal and informal economies. These mutual gains entail the organised sector to acquire and recoup lost precious metals, giving a boost to resource management along with employment generation, improved financial and health conditions and reduced pollution due to the deployment of scientific recovery methods, for those employed in the informal sector.

4.1. Seelampur Case Study

In Seelampur, a densely populated area in Delhi, hundreds of waste collectors form the largest informal resource of e-waste recovery. These informal recyclers are exposed daily to hazardous chemicals as they go about running waste recovery operations without any scientific approach. This has posed serious concerns regarding their well-being and health. As the volume of e-waste handled by the informal sector at Seelampur is expansive, their importance cannot be negated (Sreedhar, 2019).

In the past few years, the hazards of unscientific recovery of e-waste have been acknowledged by the unorganised sector leading to various initiatives by the Centre government as well as NGOs to educate and formalise this sector for capacity building and assistance of these workers, by encouraging them to use scientific methods for recovery of precious metals from the e-waste. Besides, machinery and various equipment are being provided to them for better management of e-waste recovery. Due to this, adverse environmental consequences have been reduced to a certain extent along with the expert advice, capacity building efforts, sensitisation and access to formal markets have further improved their economic conditions.

On the other hand, the government institutions and organisations are instrumental in motivating this sector by setting up and encouraging e-waste

management in the Seelampur area. The Centre government's focus is to scientifically encourage waste segregation through various certified capacity-building initiatives. Implementing such changes is an extremely tough task for the government, but various policies like the Delhi Master Plan are focusing on controlling and minimising unscientific recycling efforts and shifting such hazardous activities away from the populated areas of the capital.

Seelampur is an area of interest and research for study, and various NGOs and research facilities are working towards collecting and measuring further information on the harmful side effects of such unorganised activities and the increase in pollution volume. All these studies endorsed the reinforcement of the wide-reaching administrative control and justifiable models of refurbishing and recycling with long-term sustainability in mind. Various reports are constantly being released by organisations like 'Toxics Link' and many others which are continuously updating about areas where pollution is concentrated and also monitoring the health statistics and economic trends in Seelampur's unorganised recycling business.

4.2. Chintan NGO E-waste Management Case Study

The second case study is of Chintan, a New Delhi based NGO, operating for more than a decade, and is helping the informal e-waste collectors of the region. They have formed a group of twelve thousand strong informal e-waste collectors known as the Safai Sena. This group is focusing on the 4Rs of recycling which are Refuse, Reuse, Reduce and Recycle. They are focused on keeping down the e-waste generated and utilising the products recovered in recycling and refurbishing (Chaturvedi & Bhardwaj, 2013).

Chintan is providing numerous provisions to these workers like healthcare centres, education along with economic aid (Chintan Environmental Research and Action Group, n.d.).

This outlook has various constructive outcomes such as enabling greater safety for workers along with the provision of prompt healthcare facilities, protection from side effects of handling hazardous substances due to sensitisation and

provision of scientific equipment. Besides enhanced and improved financial conditions, stability, and easy access to social security and services, Chintan's approach to safe handling and recycling of products also helped in reducing contamination due to unscientific handling, thus reducing overall pollution.

The NGO's continuous efforts in creating awareness about the actual hazards and pathetic conditions of the workers also influenced worker-centric policy changes to enable the unorganised sector to become a part of the mainstream.

The organisation is focused on assisting the informal e-waste sector, which is also known as 'Kabadiwalas' in India, and is striving to make way for these informal workers in the formal resource recovery markets. The workers are being taught the scientific viability of e-waste recycling methods and also focus is on capacity enhancement along with reduction in exposure to hazardous substances. Chintan also has an e-waste collection and management method wherein they have joint forces with educational institutes, private sectors and various government organisations.

The organisation is working by implementing India's 2016 E-Waste Management Rules (MoEFCC, 2016), where EPR is a primary component, in which the producers of electronics have to be an active actor in the life cycle of the electronic product. The capacity gaps are being bridged to bring the informal workers at par with the formal e-waste recycling sector, along with collaboration with various industries which have to give compliance of EPR.

Safe refurbishing provisions, which are a prerequisite towards the induction of workers in the formal sector, are being provided to the workers along with constantly updating them through capacity-building initiatives.

4.3. A Case Study of Brazil

The National Solid Waste Management Policy 2010, in Brazil, introduced the concept of 'reverse logistical responsibility' and demanded that all the actors involved in the entire producer chain (manufacturing companies, distributors, importers and retailers) take responsibility to organise points of collection for the

e-waste generated by their products. Moreover, the law encourages different sectors and municipalities to involve cooperatives and other organisations of collectors of recyclable or reusable materials in their e-waste management plans (Brazilian NR, 2017). After approving the waste management law, National Solid Waste Policy, the Ministry of Environment and the Brazilian Support Service for Micro and Small Enterprises (SEBRAE) signed an agreement to develop projects and programmes to promote environmental sustainability and build technical and management capacity in e-waste management for small and medium enterprises, in the context of the new rules. For this purpose, the government launched the project Eco-Electro which provides training to solid waste management cooperatives on the separation and dismantling of e-waste. Cooperatives also receive guidance on how to sell the different fractions of recyclable electronics to ensure that they are delivered to certified buyers who can adequately treat e-waste.

Therefore, it becomes crucial for governments in India to address the capacity constraints, technological constraints, etc., to handhold and provide sufficient support for enabling the corporatisation of the e-waste economy. Some suggestions in this regard would be the interest subvention scheme for cooperatives involved in e-waste management, industrial parks for e-waste management, Capex support and collection-linked incentives adhering to quality standards, encouraging and incentivising multinational companies involved in the higher end of the value chain by providing tax breaks for adhering to processing targets and EPR norms and mandatory enforcement of EPR norms by monitoring company EPR strategies by periodic reporting.

5. Policy Recommendations for Effective Integration of the Informal Sector into the Formal Sector

The formalisation of the informal sector through cooperatives, mechanisms through which integrations can be made possible, and the role played by various supporting actors, like government and non-state actors, in enabling this synergy will be expanded upon in this section.

5.1. Synergising Collection Efficiency of the Informal Sector and Processing Efficiency of the Formal Sector

The informal sector, which includes waste pickers and scavengers, plays a critical role in collecting and sorting waste in many developing countries. Whereas in the usual course, processing of waste products and their suitable recycling is being handled by the formal sector in European Countries (PRO Europe), which includes actors like the government bodies, in case of India, most are under the purview of municipal corporations and various firms handling waste disposal and management.

The collaboration between the formal and informal sectors must start right at the sorting stage. So that through proper training and capacity building initiatives, and with better knowledge, more recyclables are recovered at the initial crucial stage itself.

The informal sector can be incentivised to segregate waste by offering higher prices for recyclable materials or by providing training on the benefits of waste segregation. The formal sector can invest in developing recycling infrastructure to process the waste collected by the informal sector. This can include setting up recycling plants, composting facilities, and waste-to-energy plants.

In Brazil, the main actors in charge of collecting, dismantling and separating e-waste fractions are currently collectors (cooperatives, small businesses and individuals), as consumers are not yet aware of the importance of separating e-waste. As the National Solid Waste Policy is progressively implemented through systems of reverse logistics, cooperatives and small businesses will have the opportunity to play a substantial role and partner with formal (and certified) recycling plants within a formal e-waste recycling system. This leaves room for

cooperative enterprises to engage in the collection and to establish agreements with large manufacturers, distributors and retailers to increase the volume of e-waste and reduce the costs of transportation. The involvement of these actors will be urgent and essential in the face of current and future e-waste generation rates, particularly as the government hopes to eventually close all sanitary landfills. As an emerging economy with a relatively well-developed legal framework on e-waste, Brazil could take advantage of the opportunity to collect and potentially import e-waste and develop the processes and facilities to extract valuable materials from it.

Any business plan accompanying the formation of an organisation must be well grounded in the current context (legislation, rules, value chain, prices, etc.) and must envision future changes and trends in the dynamics of the value chain in order to remain competitive against new market entrants. Moreover, e-waste recycling is a sector with high private sector involvement, and organisations of collectors and dismantlers will benefit from key partnerships with companies practising EPR. Partnerships with bulk producers, in particular, are key to accessing large amounts of e-waste and ensuring secure income. Organisations of collectors need to promote their role in the two phases of collection and transportation between e-waste producers and formal recyclers. Likewise, legislation must encourage and incentivise informal recyclers to adopt environmentally responsible practices. Alternatively, legislation could require EEE manufacturing and distribution companies to fund the e-waste price gap between formal and informal sources as part of the country's EPR scheme.

5.2. Role of Government in Formalising the Informal Sector

The informal sector plays a significant role in the economy of many developing countries. Capital deficit and socio-economic protection, and half-baked, unscientific methods being deployed by the informal sector, impede the capacity and capability of the informal sector, thereby reducing their productivity and causing a great loss in exploring the full economic potential of e-waste. By giving them access to assistance and modern infrastructure, their integration into the formal economy would be at a faster pace.

These practices have already brought significant changes in the sector in many other countries. For example, Brazil has come up with a national e-waste management system, which has encouraged capacity-building initiatives and worked towards formalising the informal e-waste sector. Brazil is not only

providing incentives to the informal sectors but has also set up collection facilities for e-waste for better management of the sector.

Colombia has also come up with the E-Nation waste management system and is working on similar lines. The informal sector has been integrated with the formal one, and many initiatives to improve health and safety concerns of the workers have been undertaken by promoting sustainability in the e-waste management sector, along with capacity building initiatives.

Ghana has already formalised the informal e-waste sector through various capacity-building initiatives, providing safety measures to the sector and also incorporated the e-waste policy as part of the national e-waste management system. South Africa also has a national e-waste management system striving towards enhanced and capacity-building efforts and providing many incentives to workers, and also facilitating collection centres and encouraging collaboration between both formal and informal sectors.

The case studies of these countries depict how sustainability can be encouraged through policy interventions and initiatives, and by giving a formal status to the unorganised informal e-waste sector.

Incentives, along with capacity building and innovation are the major tools a vast majority of countries are deploying to achieve this. Mandating regulations and providing legal status to the sector will further acknowledge the importance of this long-neglected sector. The Indian government can take initiatives towards formalising the unorganised sector by establishing a legal and regulatory framework that acknowledges and controls informal economic activity. This can include rules that support health and safety standards, licensing and registration requirements, and laws that safeguard the rights of unorganised workers. Financial inclusion is another important aspect, especially for smaller businesses and workers in the unorganised sector.

Various management programmes for small businesses, vocational training and imparting scientific knowledge along with social protection, health and unemployment insurance and bringing the unorganised sector under the ambit of various pension schemes can further give a boost to the unorganised sector. Rolling out entrepreneurial programmes, providing and funding marketplaces for better access to pool their products along with transportation facilities and infrastructure enhancement would go a long way in formalising the unorganised e-waste sector.

Government can also encourage the private sector to utilise the services of these workers, pool the joint resources and technology and guarantee them minimum wages. This would allow a level playing field for all the actors and be mutually beneficial in the long run.

The government of India has already passed the E-waste Management Rules, 2016 (MoEFCC, 2016), which have formulated various regulatory reforms and reiterated the socio-economic benefits of the e-waste value chain.

By focusing on EPR, the MoEFCC in 2016 extended the responsibility of channelising the e-waste collection and recycling to the producers. This has made the industry responsible towards their role in closing the material loop in the e-waste management chain, besides increases their responsibility in overall e-waste management, through buy-back offers, handling and dismantling of hazardous products utilised in manufacturing, safe transportation, etc. (MoEFCC, 2016).

Collaborating with the informal sector and its representatives, such as local NGOs, is a key component for scaling up the implementation of such strategies. The rules allow flexibility in how producers meet their responsibilities, they may do so individually or collectively. For an individual approach, producers can establish collection centres, operate in-house take-back systems, or initiate buy-back programmes on their own. Alternatively, for a collective approach, producers can partner with a PRO. Additionally, the rules propose two complementary tools to support the fulfilment of EPR obligations, E-waste Exchange and Deposit Refund Schemes. Regardless of the chosen approach, producers in India must understand and comply with the requirements of the current EPR framework, such as those outlined in the E-Waste Management Rules, 2016 (Henzler et al., 2018). E-waste management rules are withdrawing the rights from the informal collectors to register collection centres. In order to proceed, they have to abide by the rules and get themselves registered in accordance with signed contracts with producers or PROs to procure the material on their behalf.

The state of Telangana in India, has formulated and implemented systems and methods on the basis of Telangana's e-waste laws for addressing the environmental and technological challenges arising due to e-waste. These systems allow the producers to adhere to the guidelines and proceed with approved recycling centres and establish the e-waste procurement in line with these regulations. Municipal authorities are actively launching awareness

programmes for the public to address the hazards associated with irregular waste disposal in the environment and making them literate towards the merits of using established facilities.

Telangana keeps a keen eye on the e-waste management sector when it comes to technology and e-waste business, maintaining Hyderabad as a focal point of the tech hub. Companies in these sectors are encouraged to manage their e-waste responsibly and comply with EPR requirements. Some IT companies in Telangana partner with certified recyclers to ensure secure data destruction and environmentally sound recycling of obsolete equipment.

Considering the best practices like in Telangana, the Indian government should focus on the steps to support the informal sector in e-waste management and promote its formalisation. The E-waste Management Rules, enacted by the government, regulate key aspects of e-waste handling, including its collection, transportation, and disposal. These rules mandate that formal e-waste recyclers obtain authorisation and provide guidelines for the safe handling and processing of e-waste. However, the rules also acknowledge the crucial role of the informal sector and include provisions to integrate its actors into the formal e-waste management system.

5.3. Role of the Cooperative Model in Effective Integration of the Informal Sector into the Formal E-waste Recycling Chain

Collaborating with local interface agencies can facilitate the establishment of efficient systems for collecting and recovering precious materials. Since conducting an ex-ante analysis can demand significant internal resources, a more practical approach for producers and PROs can be to work with locally integrated interface agencies, such as NGOs or waste collectors' cooperatives. These organisations typically have relevant tacit knowledge of existing informal practices and have established connections within the e-waste sector.

Establishing appropriate agreements and protocols (including payment systems) is crucial for the success of partnerships between the formal and informal sectors. These agreements can be either non-binding and flexible or highly detailed with legally enforceable terms. Regardless of the type of agreement, producers and PROs should ensure that the payments they provide are not minimal but realistic and sufficient to bridge the income gap between the formal

and informal sectors. Effective protocols should specify reporting intervals, define material quality standards, and include provisions related to occupational aspects. The technical details of these agreements and protocols should be discussed with the partnering organisation. Initiating partnerships with larger collectors and aggregators can also help boost collection rates.

Given the fragmented nature of the informal economy, it is recommended that producers and PROs form partnerships with organisations that have relevant connections with informal collectors and can help achieve collection targets. Ideally, these partner organisations include leaders from informal communities who can serve as key points of contact and enhance the overall effectiveness of collection efforts. Providing information on the formalisation of informal collectors in downstream processes can also add credibility to EPR plans. Since the E-Waste Management Rules, 2016 (MoEFCC, 2016), the E-Waste (Management) Rules, 2022 (MoEFCC, 2022), E-Waste First Amendment Rules (MoEFCC, 2023a) and E-Waste Second Amendment Rules, 2023 (MoEFCC, 2023c) do not explicitly address partnerships with informal collectors, producers are advised to describe their formalisation strategies qualitatively for e.g. by emphasising collaboration with local interface agencies that promote formalisation.

The performance of partnerships should be closely monitored, routinely evaluated, and developed with a long-term perspective. In some cases, interface agencies may not have the required resources or capacity to engage a sufficient number of informal collectors. When this occurs, producers and PROs should offer direct support and help strengthen their capacities. To ensure that relationships with the informal sector are both sustainable and cost-effective, they must be viewed as long-term investments. As part of the monitoring and evaluation process, creating a detailed implementation schedule can benefit the producers and PROs.

Transparency is essential for building successful partnerships with producers and PROs. Ideally, interface agencies should clearly explain the pricing of their e-waste collection services to these stakeholders. If such pricing frameworks are not already in place, they should be developed collaboratively through a step-by-step process. Transparency is also critical to prevent collected e-waste from re-entering the informal sector. Implementing transparency mechanisms, such as web-based applications, can enable real-time tracking of material flow and ensure accountability across the e-waste value chain. It is likely that regular revisions to the structure of partnerships are necessary when deviations from

agreed-upon protocols are observed. For producers and PROs, partnerships with the informal sector should be seen as long-term investments, where building mutual trust and respectful relationships is key to success. Achieving this requires an iterative learning process involving producers, PROs, interface agencies, and the informal sector.

Selecting an appropriate combination of incentives for informal collectors is crucial. Therefore, interface agencies should assess the need for specific non-financial interventions within informal networks, e.g. provision of ID cards, healthcare, promoting workers' rights, and communicate these needs to producers or PROs. While monetary incentives are typically preferred in transactions between the formal and informal sectors, it is important that producers understand and are encouraged to offer payments aligned with market rates. Ultimately, interface agencies must ensure that the chosen mix of monetary and non-monetary incentives offers a strong enough impetus for informal collectors to channel e-waste into formal systems (Henzler et al., 2018).

6. Potential of Cooperatives

Cooperatives can provide a platform for informal waste pickers and recyclers to organise and collaborate with formal recyclers, manufacturers, and other stakeholders in the e-waste recycling chain. To educate the informal garbage collectors in reference to financing and technologies, cooperatives can play a key role and give rise to a class of skilled and efficient collectors who can yield a better quality of recycled waste. It will also uplift their standard of living by equipping them with a better hand in bargaining for their skilled services through the channels of organised markets and assistance from cooperatives.

Environment-friendly systems can also be infused in the environment with the help of cooperatives to subsidise the hazardous effects of waste disposal in an inorganic manner by streamlining the handling, managing, segregating and disposing of hazardous waste. Cooperatives can play a vital role in reducing the ill effects of unorganised e-waste disposal on the atmosphere as well as human health by keeping adequate checks on the implemented procedures in the system.

A deep study is required to assess the point of view from all the stakeholders to formulate an integrated strategy, benefitting both the formal as well as the informal sectors. This includes collectors, dismantlers, aggregators and their willingness to formalise.

Even though the collection efficiency in terms of quantity is high in the informal sector, many anomalies exist with this method of e-waste collection. Owing to a lack of technology, capital and scalability issues as an outcome of the individualised nature of the collection, the worker is always at a disadvantage. When formed as a collective, there is better bargaining power and better negotiation of prices in contrast to collecting individually as part of the informal sector. Higher price realisation can lead to higher profits and a surplus for capital investment in productive technologies and machinery. When collectors and recyclers are formed as a collective, they can better arrange working hours and ensure the division of labour in a scientific manner by dividing collection, segregation, cleaning, sorting, crushing duties, etc., thereby reducing the intensity of labour and physical burden of work. It is pertinent to note that worker cooperatives can enhance the awareness of workers in occupational safety and health as they deal with hazardous substances.

These e-waste cooperatives could be made in line with the Farmer Producer Organisations (FPO) where the government support is in the form of a grant of matching equity, i.e. cash infusion of up to INR10 lakhs to registered FPOs and providing credit guarantee cover to lending institutions, i.e. maximum guarantee covers 85% of loans not exceeding INR100 lakhs (Farm Sector Policy Department & Farm Sector Development Department, 2015). Like the FPOs, the government can formulate policies to make many consortia of informal e-waste collectors, which can support the development of e-waste cooperatives and the National E-waste Market, which aims to create a unified national market for e-waste commodities. This can increase the refurbishing and recycling of e-waste manifolds and provide greater market access for e-waste cooperatives. The National Cooperative Development Corporation (NCDC) can be extended to incorporate e-waste cooperatives in the eligible institutions' list to receive support under the various programmes of the corporation. Implementing state-level e-waste policies to support and strengthen these e-waste cooperatives will make them feasible, sustainable and self-governing bodies.

7. Conclusion

The absence of official structures and norms distinguishes the unorganised sector from the organised sector. The process of formalising any sector is intricate and takes time; it frequently calls for combining changes to rules and regulations with initiatives to increase wealth creation and productivity. Reducing decent work deficiencies is the first step towards a longer-term progressive formalisation of any sector.

It is evident from the notable decline in informal sectors in many nations that attaining outcomes is relatively achievable. Formalising the e-waste sector through cooperatives will engage in value-adding operations and open new business prospects, much like farmers' and producers' agricultural cooperative organisations, whose primary goals are to maximise the purchase and production of farm products along with processing and access to the market.

When the unorganised e-waste sector comes together and works to create a formal cooperative society, they will have more negotiating power. They will collectively be able to determine reasonable pricing for their products. This will save the sector from losses as well.

Formalising the sector will also increase their collective marketing power and will give them better access to markets. Once the sector is organised, the e-waste collectors can also engage in value-adding operations, opening new business prospects as formal channels will open for them through capacity building, access to the producers and refurbishers, processing facilities, banking and price determination for their products, which shall further prevent their exploitation. Also, adverse effects on health can be avoided once crude methods of metal extraction from e-waste are reduced.

New tax incentives are generated by formal economies, which also eliminate the financial obligations left by the informal sector, as informal, unorganised sectors have no contribution to the economy. There is also a large wage disparity between the organised and unorganised sectors at present. A coordinated and all-encompassing strategy involving the public, commercial, and non-profit sectors is needed to formalise the unorganised sector. A more inclusive and advanced economy depends on tackling the issues encountered by workers in the unorganised sector, independent of economic policy considerations.

According to the ILO, contrary to the old forecasts, informality has not diminished over time and is even increasing in many countries. Spike in poverty rates and decline in skilled work are inherent attributes of an informal economy, which can be overcome through addressing the informal channels of businesses. In 2015, the ILO adopted the 'Transition from the Informal to the Formal Economy Recommendation' (ILO, 2017). In order to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals, many more countries have participated in the world by creating strategies and policies focusing on the bridge to formality.

Focusing on the informal workers, the Indian government has also taken numerous initiatives towards the skill development and empowerment of these workers. Among all, the foremost policy is to streamline the process of handling, segregating, and processing the e-waste in line with health and safety measures. Next came the recognition of official workers by awarding them through the channels of subsidies, tax exemptions, and other monetary aids. The third step came in educating them through various learning initiatives in reference to the pros and cons of formal disposal channels. A few instances of these are providing financial aid to recycling plants, collection centres, etc.

Due to recycling, Indian e-waste industries can benefit to a great extent from the enhancement of new business avenues. As per the India Ratings and Research report published recently, this sector can grow at a CAGR of 13.52%, and by the year, the total revenue can reach \$198.52 million (India Ratings and Research, 2025).

The Government of India has already formulated and implemented e-waste policies in the country, looking at the benefits of formalising the e-waste sector. Policy formulation in this regard can take the sector towards sustainable practices while increasing revenue generation and employment opportunities.

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